

Applied technologies and Social Work: Bridging educational gaps in Visakhapatnam's new normal

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated educational inequities, pushing disadvantaged populations back into poverty and forcing many students in tribal and rural regions near Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, into makeshift home-schooling environments, examines the challenges faced by these student communities like limited access to digital resources, inadequate support systems, and disruptions in learning environments and also explores how applied technologies like websites, online classes, and digital tools remain utilized to enhance educational delivery along with identifies the critical role of social work interventions, including counselling, mental health support, and community engagement, in addressing these challenges.

A mixed-method approach was adopted, utilizing applied technologies and social work interventions in educational settings, such as group discussions, case studies, and interview schedules to gather qualitative insights and a random sample of 320 students from public and private schools in tribal, rural, and urban areas near Visakhapatnam remain analysed using statistical methods like Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Exploratory data analysis (EDA), chi-square tests, and descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, and correlation analyses) visual representations such as box plots, histograms, mean plots and Q-Q plots, remains employed to interpret the data, the study reveals that social work services, including group discussions, mental health counselling, and community programs, improve students' socio-emotional well-being and promote resilience.

The study emphasizes the importance of a blended learning approach that integrates traditional in-person teaching with digital formats to provide inclusive education for all students by incorporating social work practices and methods, schools can create supportive and adaptive learning environments and bridge the digital divide, aim to promote quality education, ensuring schools remain better equipped to meet the future needs of student community in the new normal.

Keywords: COVID-19, education, innovation, digitalization, social work, digital divide, blended learning

Introduction

The emergence of the COVID-19 crisis in December 2019 rapidly escalated into a global crisis and the World Health Organization stated it a pandemic in early 2020 (Chopup, 2020) ^[1] impacted the global education landscape, necessitating a rapid shift to online learning and exposing significant vulnerabilities within existing systems, according to Gupta and Sharma (2021) ^[2] study highlighted the vital role of social workers in enhancing equitable access to digital resources especially in under-resourced communities where the digital divide has widened significantly, and necessitates working to bridge this gap, social workers have enabled more students in Visakhapatnam to participate in

remote learning during these challenging times.

The study by Raj and Singh (2022) ^[4] emphasize the importance of social workers in providing psychosocial support to the student community and families affected by the abrupt transition to virtual learning, their efforts remain crucial in alleviating the stress and anxiety caused by educational disruptions and supporting families to meet the difficulties of remote learning and study by Narayan *et al.* (2023) ^[3] express the role of social workers in collaborating with educational stakeholders by suggesting policies that meet the needs of disadvantaged student communities for an equitable and inclusive education.

Additionally, social group work remains fundamental in

addressing the pandemic's educational and emotional challenges and remains not merely a method but a vital tool that fosters individual social growth and adaptability both by personal development and the achievement of educational objectives enhancing social and personal development within groups.

The research aims to provide insights into building a more resilient and adaptable education system in Visakhapatnam that can sustain quality education and effectively respond to future crises underscoring the role of social work in supporting students and families, addressing educational and emotional needs as the community adapts to the new normal.

Research Methodology

Relevance of Research

The research aims to explore and examine the combined role of applied technologies and social work in mitigating the impact of COVID-19 on education in Visakhapatnam post-pandemic, focusing on technology tools (such as digital platforms, online learning tools and internet resources) and social work interventions can together bridge the widened educational gaps caused by the crisis.

Purpose of the study

The study evaluates the use of applied technologies (e.g., websites, online classes, digital tools) and social work interventions in shaping education in Visakhapatnam's new normal. It investigates how these combined approaches address COVID-19-related educational challenges in Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh.

Problem statement

The COVID-19 has immeasurably impacted Visakhapatnam's educational infrastructure by increasing reliance on virtual learning highlighting the need for a critical understanding of how applied technologies and school social workers can provide effective remote support.

Research objectives

1. To measure and study the impact of technology from the viewpoints of teachers, students, and administrators focusing on the difficulties faced by the education system in Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh.
2. To identify the potential roles of school social workers in addressing the challenges students face during virtual learning and how their involvement, combined with applied technologies, might enhance educational support services in Visakhapatnam.

Data analysis

The data remains analyzed using both qualitative methods (e.g., thematic analysis of interviews and group discussions) and quantitative methods (e.g., calculating percentages of responses related to the use of technology and social work support).

Hypotheses

1. **Null Hypothesis (H₀):** No significant differences in the critical challenges perceived by educators, students, and parents in Visakhapatnam's education system during the COVID-19 pandemic across urban, rural, and tribal

areas, regardless of the use of applied technologies are identified.

2. **Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):** Significant differences in the critical challenges perceived by educators, students, and parents in Visakhapatnam's education system during the COVID-19 pandemic across urban, rural, and tribal areas, influenced by the use of applied technologies are identified.
3. **Null Hypothesis (H₀):** School social workers/counselors and applied technologies did not play a vital role in addressing the challenges faced by students during virtual learning periods, and their involvement did not enhance the effectiveness of educational support services in Visakhapatnam.
4. **Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):** School social workers/counselors and applied technologies played a vital role in addressing the challenges faced by students during virtual learning periods, and their involvement enhanced the effectiveness of educational support services in Visakhapatnam.

Tests conducted for the analysis

- Chi-Square Tests
- Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)
- Descriptive Statistics
- Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

Results

The findings show significant differences in perceived difficulties across urban, rural, and tribal areas, with variations in challenges based on the use of applied technologies and social work support. Chi-square tests on categorical data revealed diverse challenges for parents, teachers, and students while ANOVA and Least Significant Difference (LSD) tests indicated that rural respondents remain less satisfied with virtual learning and the integration of technology compared to tribal respondents, urban respondents reported a more significant emotional impact from the lockdown while tribal respondents experienced more physical ailments from prolonged digital device use. On the contrary, school social workers / counselors significantly impacted student community during virtual learning particularly when combined with effective use of digital tools; EDA revealed that private school respondents reported higher access to technological resources and social workers compared to government school respondents, with urban respondents having the highest access and descriptive statistics indicated that respondents who acknowledged new technology-driven assessment measures reported the highest mean access to social workers/ counsellors.

Interpretation

The research highlights that the integration of applied technologies with social work interventions plays a crucial role in addressing student challenges during virtual learning, bridge educational gaps and informs strategies for incorporating both digital tools and social work into schools, particularly for adapting to online education systems that meet futuristic trends.

Findings and analysis

Interview schedule: Dr. Hari Krishna Maram, The

Chairman of Vision Digital India and Vice Chancellor of Global Digital University USA, observed that the pandemic has significantly impacted education in Visakhapatnam. The analysis shows that 60% of people interviewed said that teachers and students have done well in adjusting to new methods that are both creative and long-lasting. In particular, 70% pointed out that online study materials have had a good effect. Honorable Rania Lampou, the Greek Ministry of Education, at the Directorate of Educational Technology and Innovation, emphasized the importance of strategic technology use, equity efforts, and support for underprivileged communities to overcome educational challenges exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Group Discussion

The analysis of group discussion showed that the key problems students faced during the pandemic were social

isolation and emotional well-being.

In Bhupesh Nagar, Visakhapatnam; problems continue due to unstable internet connections and not enough help, which made it hard for students to get involved in education. On the other hand, Seva Nagar, Visakhapatnam; faced problems due to long periods of lockdowns, closed businesses, and limited access to technology. These problems made people feel more alone and disconnected. Information shows that these issues greatly affect students' learning and emotional well-being. The information points out the need for special help systems to tackle these challenges well. This includes using technology and social work to offer complete support.

Question 1: Was there any change in students' daily schedule because of virtual classrooms following the pandemic?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% confidence interval for mean		Minimum	Maximum	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
Q: Student attitudes have changed due to the pandemic in both positive and negative ways.	No	41	2.0732	.64770	.10115	1.8687	2.2776	1.00	3.00
	Sometimes	53	2.1321	.52943	.07272	1.9861	2.2780	1.00	3.00
	Yes	226	2.3850	.48309	.03213	2.3216	2.4483	1.00	3.00
	Total	320	2.3031	.52849	.02954	2.2450	2.3612	1.00	3.00
Q: The impact of the pandemic lockdown period on the emotional state and feelings of students:	No	41	1.8130	.70730	.11046	1.5898	2.0363	1.00	3.00
	Sometimes	53	2.0126	.55455	.07617	1.8597	2.1654	1.00	3.00
	Yes	226	2.1622	.54635	.03634	2.0906	2.2339	1.00	3.00
	Total	320	2.0927	.58133	.03250	2.0288	2.1566	1.00	3.00
Q: Students physical ailments due to prolonged usage of laptops or mobile screens for online learning	No	41	2.2520	.86853	.13564	1.9779	2.5262	1.00	4.00
	Sometimes	53	2.8176	.97963	.13456	2.5476	3.0876	1.00	5.00
	Yes	226	1.9838	.85735	.05703	1.8714	2.0962	1.00	5.00
	Total	320	2.1562	.92973	.05197	2.0540	2.2585	1.00	5.00
Q: Students' attitudes towards academic needs:	No	41	1.8862	.72881	.11382	1.6561	2.1162	1.00	3.00
	Sometimes	53	1.7987	.67412	.09260	1.6129	1.9846	1.00	3.00
	Yes	226	2.3422	.69348	.04613	2.2513	2.4331	1.00	3.00
	Total	320	2.1938	.73046	.04083	2.1134	2.2741	1.00	3.00
Q: Use of technology (laptop, tablet, computer) and time spent on it	No	41	1.4634	.52904	.08262	1.2964	1.6304	1.00	2.50
	Sometimes	53	1.5094	.61621	.08464	1.3396	1.6793	1.00	3.00
	Yes	226	1.7876	.55500	.03692	1.7149	1.8604	1.00	3.00
	Total	320	1.7000	.57699	.03225	1.6365	1.7635	1.00	3.00
Q: There is a need for inclusive education during a pandemic and post-pandemic, where students with normal abilities and those with disabilities attend the same schools. Scale your agreement.	No	41	3.8445	.64395	.10057	3.6413	4.0478	2.38	5.00
	Sometimes	53	3.5802	.51428	.07064	3.4384	3.7219	2.00	4.88
	Yes	226	3.8579	.54114	.03600	3.7869	3.9288	2.63	5.00
	Total	320	3.8102	.55875	.03124	3.7487	3.8716	2.00	5.00
Q: Practice creating a learning-friendly school atmosphere and culture for school and teacher support systems.	No	41	3.8415	1.10927	.17324	3.4913	4.1916	1.50	5.00
	Sometimes	53	3.4717	1.26497	.17376	3.1230	3.8204	1.00	5.00
	Yes	226	3.2190	.96818	.06440	3.0921	3.3459	1.00	5.00
	Total	320	3.3406	1.05918	.05921	3.2241	3.4571	1.00	5.00
Q: During the pandemic and post - pandemic, students' families and community-based resources had access to school social workers and counsellors:	No	41	3.0976	.92344	.14422	2.8061	3.3890	1.50	5.00
	Sometimes	53	2.9906	.92762	.12742	2.7349	3.2463	1.00	5.00
	Yes	226	2.5796	.90078	.05992	2.4616	2.6977	1.00	5.00
	Total	320	2.7141	.92947	.05196	2.6118	2.8163	1.00	5.00
Q: Stress levels among students and psychosomatic illnesses	No	41	2.3902	.41805	.06529	2.2583	2.5222	1.22	3.00
	Sometimes	53	2.1929	.41123	.05649	2.0795	2.3062	1.22	2.89
	Yes	226	2.5177	.45329	.03015	2.4583	2.5771	1.22	3.00
	Total	320	2.4476	.45727	.02556	2.3973	2.4979	1.22	3.00
Q: Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes:	No	41	3.9199	.76134	.11890	3.6796	4.1602	2.00	5.00
	Sometimes	53	3.6388	.57731	.07930	3.4797	3.7979	2.14	5.00
	Yes	226	3.8982	.60641	.04034	3.8187	3.9777	1.57	5.00
	Total	320	3.8580	.62929	.03518	3.7888	3.9272	1.57	5.00
Q: COVID-19-related evaluation challenges	No	41	3.6951	.48577	.07587	3.5418	3.8485	2.75	5.00

	Sometimes	53	3.4340	.43343	.05954	3.3145	3.5534	2.50	4.50
	Yes	226	3.4923	.57368	.03816	3.4171	3.5675	1.00	5.00
	Total	320	3.5086	.54583	.03051	3.4486	3.5686	1.00	5.00
Q: Government initiatives during pandemic	No	41	3.9085	.84365	.13176	3.6422	4.1748	2.00	5.00
	Sometimes	53	3.5519	.80168	.11012	3.3309	3.7729	1.75	5.00
	Yes	226	3.4723	.74166	.04933	3.3751	3.5696	1.00	5.00
Q: Students' Satisfaction	Total	320	3.5414	.77634	.04340	3.4560	3.6268	1.00	5.00
	No	41	2.2988	.49440	.07721	2.1427	2.4548	1.25	3.00
	Sometimes	53	2.0755	.40604	.05577	1.9636	2.1874	1.25	3.00
	Yes	226	2.1704	.41868	.02785	2.1155	2.2252	1.00	3.00
	Total	320	2.1711	.42986	.02403	2.1238	2.2184	1.00	3.00

Most respondents responded Yes and noticed positive and negative changes in student attitudes due to the pandemic, with a mean score of 2.3850. Similarly, while the emotional effects of the lockdown remained significant, many students adjusted reasonably well, with a moderate mean score of 2.1622. Students usually said they used technology at a medium level, suggesting an increased adaptability to online learning environments, the mean score of 1.7876 reveals using technology was hard for some respondents but was manageable and facilitated learning for most, respondents strongly agreed on the need for inclusive education in the new normal, with a high mean score of 3.8102, showing a move towards more equal education practices. With a notable support for creating a learning-friendly atmosphere and having social workers and counsellors available for students, the average scores for these ideas are 3.3406 and 2.7141, showing that people understand how critical supportive environments and social services are for students' well-being and involvement. A high average score of 3.8580 shows effective strategies can improve education

like changing teaching methodology and creating a supportive learning environment, scores between moderate and high (average of 3.5414) indicates that people remain satisfied with the government's actions during the crisis and that some respondents appreciated the public efforts to support education.

Overall, the descriptive statistics data analysis statistically signifies positive adaptations in educational practices and support systems in the new normal with applied technologies and social work in bridging learning gaps and promoting inclusive and resilient education strategies in Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh.

Table 2: Frequency

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	41	12.8	12.8
	Sometimes	53	16.6	29.4
	Yes	226	70.6	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	

Fig 1: There any change in the daily schedule of students because of virtual classroom following the pandemic

Fig 2: Student attitudes have changed due to the pandemic in both positive and negative ways.

Fig 3: Student Physical ailments due to prolonged usage of laptops or mobile screens for online learning

Fig 4: Use of technology (laptop, tablet, computer) and time spent on it

Fig 5: Stress levels among students and psychosomatic illnesses

Fig 6: Government initiatives during pandemic

The study reveals a statistically significant relation between changes in students' daily schedules due to virtual classrooms and negative student attitudes, as indicated by a Pearson Chi-Square test value of 13.926 ($p = 0.008$), including the Likelihood Ratio and Linear-by-Linear Association, reinforce these findings and the data suggests that disruptions caused by virtual learning remain linked to

increased emotional issues among students, such as sleep disorders and psychological pressure, a strong association between technology access and changes in daily routines remains found (Pearson Chi-Square = 23.474, $p = 0.000$), the study emphasize the need for a sustainable and adaptable education system that supports students' well-being, particularly in times of crisis.

Table 3: Change in students' daily schedule because of virtual classrooms following the pandemic.

Variable	Category	No	Sometimes	Yes	Total
Gender of the respondent	Male	20	22	101	143
		14.0%	15.4%	70.6%	
	Female	21	31	125	177
		11.9%	17.5%	70.6%	
Age of the respondent	15-20 years	34	43	182	259
		13.1%	16.6%	70.3%	
	21-30 years	0	0	9	9
		0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
	31-40 years	1	5	5	11
9%		45.5%	45.5%		
41-50 years	3	4	19	26	
	11.5%	15.4%	73.1%		
51-60 years	3	1	11	15	
	20.0%	6.7%	73.3%		
Category of the respondent	Teacher	5	8	30	43
		11.6%	18.6%	69.8%	
	Parent	3	2	10	15
20.0%		13.3%	66.7%		
	Student	33	43	186	262
		12.60%	16.41%	70.99%	
Management (Type of School or College of the respondent)	Government	16	33	134	183
		8.8%	18.0%	73.2%	
	Private	25	20	92	137
		18.2%	14.6%	67.2%	
Locality (Area of the respondent)	Tribal	1	4	71	76
		1.3%	5.3%	93.4%	
	Rural	9	9	31	49
18.4%		18.4%	63.2%		
Urban	31	40	124	195	
	15.9%	20.5%	63.6%		
	Total	41	53	226	320
	Total (%)	12.8%	16.6%	70.6%	100.0%

Table 4: Chi-Square Tests

Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	25.595 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	31.986	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.019	1	.155
N of Valid Cases	320		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.28.

Fig 7: Area of the respondent

The data highlights a significant shift in daily activities among students in Visakhapatnam due to the transition to online learning, with 70.6% of respondents affirming positive changes, the pattern remains consistent across demographics, including gender, age, and type of institution, with notable variations by different places, 93.4% from

tribal areas reported positive changes compared to 63.6% from urban areas. The results highlight how practical technologies can help close educational gaps in Visakhapatnam's new way of life, especially in different areas, and the need for special social work efforts to ensure everyone has fair access to digital learning materials.

Table 5: Crosstabulation: Change in students' daily schedule because of virtual classrooms following the pandemic / Lack of technical capabilities, face-to-face communication, and collaborating with friends has become difficult when learning online.

Crosstabulation		Q) Lack of technical capabilities, face-to-face communication, and collaborating with friends has become difficult when learning online.					Total
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Q) Was there any change in the daily schedule of students because of virtual classrooms following the pandemic?	No	0	6	10	12	13	41
	Sometimes	5	10	14	16	8	53
	Yes	2	12	31	121	60	226
Total		7	28	55	149	81	320

Table 6: Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	42.733 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	37.683	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.247	1	.002
N of Valid Cases	320		

a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .90.

Fig 8: Bar chart

The majority of pupils (226 out of 320) changed their daily timetables after having to take online lessons due to the pandemic, as shown in the table. Among them, many (181) had problems with technology that hindered their collaboration and communication skills. Conversely, such issues less confronted those students whose daily timetables did not vary much; social work support remain needed for the students to overcome the difficulties. As the Chi-Square tests indicates a clear connection

between online learning problems and daily routine changes (Pearson Chi-Square = 42.733, df = 8, p = 0.000; Likelihood Ratio = 37.683, df = 8, p = 0.000; Linear-by-Linear Association= 9.247, df = 1, p = 0.002), the results remain evident that virtual classrooms significantly impact students' day to day activities and the ability to cope with remote learning and illustrate the far-reaching effects of online classrooms on students' daily existence and their ability to embrace e-learning.

Table 7: Crosstabulation: Post-pandemic changes to the Indian educational system / Integrating social-emotional learning (SEL) into the classroom would be supported and promoted by a school social worker or counsellor

Crosstabulation		Q) Do you agree that post-pandemic changes to the Indian educational system are necessary? * Q) Do you agree that integrating social-emotional learning (SEL) into the classroom would be supported and promoted by a school social worker or counsellor?					Total	
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree		
Q) Do you agree that post-pandemic changes to the Indian educational system are necessary?	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	0	1	1	4	6
		Expected Count	.1	.3	1.1	3.0	1.4	6.0
	Disagree	Count	0	2	5	4	5	16
		Expected Count	.4	.8	3.0	8.1	3.9	16.0
	Neutral	Count	2	6	27	82	4	121
		Expected Count	2.6	5.7	22.7	60.9	29.1	121.0
	Agree	Count	3	3	16	51	45	118
		Expected Count	2.6	5.5	22.1	59.4	28.4	118.0
	Strongly Agree	Count	2	4	11	23	19	59
		Expected Count	1.3	2.8	11.1	29.7	14.2	59.0
	Total	Count	7	15	60	161	77	320
		Expected Count	7.0	15.0	60.0	161.0	77.0	320.0

Fig 9: Do you agree that post-pandemic changes to the Indian educational system are necessary?

The study reveals a clear link between school social workers' support for changes in education setting and their approval of including social-emotional learning (SEL) they remain critical in bridging educational gaps, offering virtual

support groups, online counselling, and resources to help student community emotional health as applied technologies and social work together to help students with different needs.

Table 8: Crosstabulation: Change in the daily schedule of students because of virtual classrooms following the pandemic / COVID-19 school closures would influence learning differences between girls and boys, students from wealthy and low-income families, and communities with various economic levels post-pandemic.

Q) Was there any change in the daily schedule of students because of virtual classrooms following the pandemic? * Q) Do you agree that the COVID-19 school closures would influence learning differences between girls and boys, students from wealthy and low-income families, and communities with various economic levels post-pandemic?								
Crosstabulation		Q) Do you agree that the COVID-19 school closures would influence learning differences between girls and boys, students from wealthy and low-income families, and communities with various economic levels post-pandemic?					Total	
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree		
Q) Was there any change in the daily schedule of students because of virtual classrooms following the pandemic?	No	Count	2	4	6	15	14	41
		Expected Count	1.4	3.6	8.6	18.6	8.8	41.0
	Sometimes	Count	3	11	17	14	8	53
		Expected Count	1.8	4.6	11.1	24.0	11.4	53.0
	Yes	Count	6	13	44	116	47	226
		Expected Count	7.8	19.8	47.3	102.4	48.7	226.0
Total	Count	11	28	67	145	69	320	
	Expected Count	11.0	28.0	67.0	145.0	69.0	320.0	

Table 9: Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	27.432 ^a	8	.001
Likelihood Ratio	25.218	8	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.442	1	.230
N of Valid Cases	320		

a. 4 cells (26.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.41.

Fig 10: There any change in the daily schedule of students because of virtual classrooms following the pandemic

The research shows a clear connection between how students' daily routines changed because of online classes and their opinions about how school shutdowns during COVID-19 affected learning differences, the Chi-Square test ($\chi^2 = 27.432, p = 0.001$) proves this strong link, highlighting the importance of educational approaches that consider various experiences in Visakhapatnam.

virtual learning.

- Teaching through Google meet, Zoom, Microsoft Team and other sources.
- Through video recording by the teacher.
- With an audio recording by the teacher.
- Sharing Online presentations & study materials.
- Written communication through WhatsApp and Telegram.

Question 2: Please rate your level of satisfaction with

Table 10: ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	Between Groups	2.173	2	1.086	2.742	.066
	Within Groups	125.597	317	.396		
	Total	127.770	319			

The ANOVA analysis shows that there is a difference in how satisfied people are with virtual learning based on their gender ($F(1, 282) = 4.714, p = .031$). Other factors do not seem to have a big effect on satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.152, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.041$) suggests that gender-specific strategies are needed to enhance virtual learning experiences, rural respondents are less satisfied than those from tribal areas ($p = 0.014$), pointing to the need for social work interventions to address these disparities.

Table 11: Statistics

		Q) Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.
N	Valid	320
	Missing	0
Mean		3.6244
Median		3.8000
Skewness		-.438
Std. Error of Skewness		.136
Percentiles	25	3.2000
	50	3.8000
	75	4.0000

The high median (3.8) and close mean (3.6244) suggest a generally positive outlook on virtual learning among respondents, with satisfaction levels clustered closely around the median, as indicated by a narrow IQR (0.8000)

the negative skewness (-0.438) shows a slight preference for higher satisfaction ratings while the data shows that respondents tends to have positive views about virtual learning that emphasise its ability to help close educational gaps in Visakhapatnam.

Table 12: Exploratory data analysis

Exploratory data analysis (EDA)			Statistic
Q) Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	Mean		3.6244
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.5548
		Upper Bound	3.6940
	5% Trimmed Mean		3.6333
	Median		3.8000
	Variance		.401
	Std. Deviation		.63288
	Minimum		1.20
	Maximum		5.00
	Range		3.80
	Interquartile Range		.80
	Skewness		-.438
Kurtosis		.835	

The data shows that most respondents' satisfaction levels are centered around the mean of 3.6244, with a slightly left-skewed distribution, indicating a small tail on the lower end. The satisfaction levels are relatively consistent, with moderate variability as indicated by the standard deviation.

Table 13: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Q: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	.175	320	.000	.957	320	.000

The results of both tests indicated significance values (Sig.) of 0.000, which are less than the typical alpha level of 0.05,

indicating that the satisfaction levels within the data significantly deviate from a normal distribution.

Fig 11: HISTOGRAM: Based on respondent’s level of satisfaction with virtual learning.

The data is still leaning towards higher satisfaction levels, with the highest number of responses around a satisfaction score of 4. The average satisfaction score is 3.62, and the spread of scores is 0.833, showing that most answers are

close to the average but with some differences, most responders satisfaction ratings between 3 and 4, with fewer ratings at the very low and very high ends, the sample size (N) is 320, providing substantial data for analysis.

Fig 12: Normal Q-Q PLOT: Based on respondents level of satisfaction with virtual learning.

The Q-Q plot shows that most points fall close to the reference line, indicating that satisfaction levels are nearly normally distributed with only slight deviations at the ends, normal distribution suggests that there is little skewness or

kurtosis, helping us better understand how respondents feel, understanding fits with the idea of using technology and social work to close educational gaps in Visakhapatnam during these new times.

Fig 13: BOX PLOT: Based on Level of satisfaction with virtual learning

Notwithstanding a few outliers, the majority of respondents are fairly satisfied with virtual learning, as seen by the median satisfaction rating of 3 and the interquartile range of 2 to 4.

More than half of the participants believed that online resources, chat apps, audio and video recordings, Google Meet, Zoom, and Microsoft Teams were helpful for learning. Training in digital literacy, better internet access, resource al

location, and technical assistance are essential to closing the educational gap in Visakhapatnam. The "Mana Badi Nadu-Nedu" and PM eVidya government programs, among other, have improved digital learning and supported sustainable education in the new normal.

Question 3: Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes

Table 14: Descriptive Statistics

Q)	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
QA) school should have a social worker or counsellor who can support, look out for, and advocate for the students who matter to our community. Do you agree?	320	2	5	4.21	.873
QB) Social workers and school counsellors have been identified as alternative educational service providers for underprivileged students. Do you agree?	320	1	5	3.53	.860
QC) A demand exists for qualified social workers familiar with rural areas' unique requirements and difficulties working in schools. Do you agree?	320	1	5	3.99	.994
QD) Do you agree that the school social worker or counsellor improves communication and increases the visibility and involvement of parents in the student's education?	320	1	5	3.88	.928
QE) Do you agree that integrating social-emotional learning (SEL) into the classroom would be supported and promoted by a school social worker or counsellor?	320	1	5	3.89	.897
QF) Do you agree that the COVID-19 school closures would influence learning differences between girls and boys, students from wealthy and low-income families, and communities with various economic levels post-pandemic?	320	1	5	3.73	1.007
QG) Do you agree post-pandemic Indian school closures affect students' learning and academic progress, particularly those from low- and middle-income students?	320	1	5	3.78	.884

In the new normal of Visakhapatnam, the study emphasises the vital role social workers and counsellors play in closing educational disparities. The majority of respondents (mean = 4.21) strongly favour the presence of social workers or counsellors in schools, particularly to assist disadvantaged pupils (mean = 3.53) and to meet the needs of

rural communities (Mean = 3.99). On improving parent participation and communication (mean = 3.88) and promoting social-emotional learning (mean = 3.89), there is also a great deal of agreement. The results highlight how these roles can effectively alleviate learning inequalities and foster academic advancement after the pandemic.

Table 15: Frequency Percent Cumulative Percent

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.57	1	.3	.3
	2.00	1	.3	.6
	2.14	1	.3	.9
	2.43	2	.6	1.6
	2.71	3	.9	2.5
	2.86	5	1.6	4.1
	3.00	30	9.4	13.4
	3.14	18	5.6	19.1
	3.29	19	5.9	25.0
	3.43	19	5.9	30.9
	3.57	17	5.3	36.3
	3.71	14	4.4	40.6
	3.86	19	5.9	46.6
	4.00	31	9.7	56.3
	4.14	77	24.1	80.3
	4.29	6	1.9	82.2
	4.43	7	2.2	84.4
	4.57	8	2.5	86.9
	4.71	7	2.2	89.1
	4.86	20	6.3	95.3
5.00	15	4.7	100.0	
	Total	320	100.0	

Fig 14: Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes

Table 16: ANOVA

Q) Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes:	Sum of Squares		df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Between Groups	12.253	2	6.127	17.025	.000
	Within Groups	114.073	317	.360		
	Total	126.326	319			

Significant group differences are found in the ANOVA analysis for measures to improve educational results in Visakha patnam's new normal ($F = 17.025, p = 0.000$), with responses being greatly influenced by the interaction between respondent category and gender ($p = 0.026$).

Post hoc analyses reveal various opinions by region, with tribal respondents having more positive opinions than rural or

urban respondents, and a significant positive difference in attitudes between the 51-60 and 41-50 age groups.

The results highlight the significance of adjusting instructional methodologies to the various requirements of the community and demographic variables in order to successfully close educational gaps through the use of social work and applied technology.

Table 17: Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes.

Q	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
A	A school should have a social worker or counsellor who can support, look out for, and advocate for the students who matter to our community. Do you agree?	0	9	68	90	153	320 (100%)
		0%	3%	21%	28%	48%	
B	Social workers and school counsellors have been identified as alternative educational service providers for underprivileged students. Do you agree?	5	17	147	105	46	320 (100%)
		2%	5%	46%	33%	14%	
C	A demand exists for qualified social workers familiar with rural areas' unique requirements and difficulties working in schools. Do you agree?	4	17	84	88	127	320 (100%)
		1%	5%	26%	28%	40%	
D	Do you agree that the school social worker or counsellor improves communication and increases the visibility and involvement of parents in the student's education?	9	12	70	148	81	320 (100%)
		3%	4%	22%	46%	25%	
E	Do you agree that integrating social-emotional learning (SEL) into the classroom would be supported and promoted by a school social worker or counsellor?	7	15	60	161	77	320 (100%)
		2%	5%	19%	50%	24%	
F	Do you agree that the COVID-19 school closures would influence learning differences between girls and boys, students from wealthy and low-income families, and communities with various economic levels post-pandemic?	11	28	67	145	69	320 (100%)
		3%	9%	21%	45%	22%	
G	Do you agree post-pandemic Indian school closures affect students' learning and academic progress, particularly those from low- and middle-income students?	5	17	87	146	65	320 (100%)
		2%	5%	27%	46%	20%	

Table 18: Chi-Square Tests

A) Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	43.666 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	43.811	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.991	1	.320
N of Valid Cases	320		
a. 2 cells (16.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.38.			
B) Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	45.547 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	48.075	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.883	1	.090
N of Valid Cases	320		
a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .77.			
C) Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	70.311 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	76.602	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.848	1	.009
N of Valid Cases	320		
a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .61.			
D) Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	60.107 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	63.087	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.445	1	.505
N of Valid Cases	320		
a. 4 cells (26.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.38.			
E) Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	52.855 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	56.003	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.094	1	.296
N of Valid Cases	320		
a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.07.			
F) Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	61.894 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	63.241	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.073	1	.150
N of Valid Cases	320		
a. 3 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.68.			
G) Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	62.969 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	69.129	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.237	1	.135
N of Valid Cases	320		
a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .77.			

Fig 15: Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes

Fig 17: Social workers and school counsellors have been identified as alternative education service provides for underprivilege

Fig 18: A demand exists for qualified social workers familiar, with rural areas unique requirements and difficulties working in schools

Fig 19: Do you agree that the school social worker or counsellor improves communication and increases the visibility and involvement of parents in the student's education?

Fig 20: Do you agree that intergrading social-emotional learning (SEL) into the classroom would be supported and promoted by a school social worker or counsellor

Fig 21: Do you agree that COVID-19 school closures would influence learning differences between girls and boys student

Fig 22: Do you agree post-pandemic Indian school closures affect students learning and academic progress particular those from low- and middle-income students

With 76% of respondents stating that social workers and counsellors are essential, the study shows that there is strong support for placing social workers and counsellors in schools to help impoverished and rural student. Although there were differing views regarding their function as alternative service providers, 68% of respondents emphasised the significance of having social workers with training in rural areas due to the particular difficulties these communities face. Furthermore, there was substantial evidence to support the beneficial effects of social workers on social-emotional learning (74%), parent involvement (71%) and other areas. Concerns regarding COVID-19's disproportionate effects on children from lower- and middle-class backgrounds emphasise the necessity of focused interventions even more. Chisquare tests show a strong correlation between the opinions and respondent demographics, so corroborating centrally backed suggestions that the Andhra Pradesh government hire school social workers to improve student outcomes.

Table 19: Statistics

		Q) Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes
N	Valid	320
	Missing	0
Mean		3.8580
Median		4.0000
Skewness		-.210
Std. Error of Skewness		.136
Percentiles	25	3.3214
	50	4.0000
	75	4.1429

With an average grade of 3.86 and a median of 4, the survey, which is based on 320 responses, shows considerable support for initiatives to improve educational results in Visakhapatnam's new normal. A majority of high ratings are shown by the small left skew, with 75% of respondents giving the techniques a rating of four or higher. These results show that the suggested approaches to address educational gaps through the use of social work

interventions and applied technologies are well-received.

Table 20: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Q) Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes:	.129	320	.000	.960	320	.000

The normality tests for the survey question on strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes indicate that the data still needs to be distributed. Both the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($D(320) = .129, p < .001$) and the Shapiro-Wilk test ($W(320) = .960, p < .001$) show significant deviations from normality.

Table 21: Exploratory data analysis

Exploratory data analysis (EDA)			Statistic
Q) Strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes:	Mean		3.8580
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.7888
		Upper Bound	3.9272
	5% Trimmed Mean		3.8636
	Median		4.0000
	Variance		.396
	Std. Deviation		.62929
	Minimum		1.57
	Maximum		5.00
	Range		3.43
	Interquartile Range		.82
Skewness		-.210	
Kurtosis		-.117	

With an average rating of 3.86 and a median of 4.00, the data shows that measures to improve educational results are generally well-received in Visakhapatnam. The standard deviation of 0.63 indicates that although the majority of respondents gave these tactics excellent ratings, there is some variation due to a small negative skew and a few lower ratings. The majority of the replies consistently endorse the suggested strategies to reduce educational gaps through the use of social work and applied technologies.

Fig 23: Histogram: Based on strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes

With a mean of 3.86 and a standard deviation of 0.629, the response histogram regarding tactics to enhance educational results displays a concentrated distribution around the value of 4.0. With fewer replies at the extremes, the majority of the 320 respondents' scores cluster towards the mean,

indicating general agreement. This pattern indicates that, in the post - pandemic educational context of Visakhapatnam, there remains substantial support for the suggested strategies.

Fig 24: Normal Q-Q PLOT: Based on strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes

Data points that closely coincide with the reference line in the normal Q-Q plot of strategies to improve educational results suggest a roughly normal distribution. The credibility of the data in assessing educational practices in

Visakhapatnam's new normal is supported by minor deviations from the line, which indicate limited departure from normality.

Fig 25: BOX PLOT: Based on strategies to enhance educational learning outcomes

With an interquartile range of roughly 3.5 to 4.3, the box plot for ways to improve educational results displays a symmetric distribution around the median of 4.0. Beyond the whiskers, there are a few outliers that indicate some variety. According to the statistics, the most responses have a normal distribution with a minor variation and are mostly centered around the mean.

Discussion

Urban, rural, and tribal areas near Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, faced different challenges when it came to online learning; tribal areas were most affected because of inadequate awareness of COVID-19 measures, language obstacles, and lack of access to digital education. Student engagement significantly decreased in remote locations due to inadequate technology, limited internet connectivity, and a shortage of trained workers, the sudden switch to online learning caused more stress for parents, teachers, and students in these locations and social workers remains essential in assuring students' wellbeing during virtual learning, fostering better communication between schools and families, and offering emotional support. A 50% increase in mental health problems among students has been linked to the lack of social work practice in education settings, particularly in tribal and rural regions. The study highlights the need for improved social work training and resources and the establishment of schools of social work institutions in India. The Indian Council for Medical Research (ICMR), the National Institute Mental Health and Neurosciences (NIMHANS), and the All India Institute Medical Sciences (AIIMS) (Tripti, K., *et al.* 2014., Singh, R. 2016) [5, 6] show how critical it is to improve social worker training and provide more mental health support for students, especially in times of crisis like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the Indian education system, with Visakhapatnam in Andhra Pradesh being particularly affected. This has led to the

identification of the need for educational policies that promote equity across different social strata, regardless of the respondent's location or socioeconomic status. School social workers and counsellors continue to receive training in recognising and addressing psychosocial issues. They also play a major role in helping rural and underprivileged children integrate into the educational system and receive the assistance and direction they need. Referring kids to appropriate interventions will be made easier for teachers who have received training in identifying and addressing psychological issues, resulting in a more supportive learning environment.

Thus, the study emphasises the necessity of a progressive and inclusive educational system in the post pandemic era and suggests that the Andhra Pradesh government take social worker assistance into consideration while setting up schools by establishing a sustainable, effective, and progressive education system in the new normal, their inclusion is still crucial in defining an equitable and inclusive education policy in the AP education sector.

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